

Foundation Model Guidance for Tattoo Retrieval

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Abstract: Tattoo recognition is a critical task in forensics; however, existing approaches often face limitations under real-world conditions such as occlusion, distortion, and low image quality. This paper presents a novel and robust tattoo retrieval framework that combines the global semantic representation capabilities of OmniGlue with the geometric precision of LightGlue. Notably, the proposed framework is entirely based on foundation models and operates in a training-free manner, enabling rapid deployment without the need for dataset-specific fine-tuning. Extensive experiments conducted on the challenging WebTattoo dataset demonstrate the effectiveness of the approach. In closed-set evaluation, the framework achieves a rank-1 identification rate of 90.91%, significantly outperforming standalone models as well as the state-of-the-art TattTRN. In open-set identification, the method attains an Equal Error Rate of 11.56%, outperforming equally the state of the art, i.e., TattTRN (20.75%). These results highlight the advantages of integrating complementary foundation models through mechanisms, establishing a new benchmark for tattoo recognition in both controlled and unconstrained environments.

Keywords: Foundation Models, OmniGlue, LightGlue, Tattoo Retrieval

1 Introduction

Tattoos are a unique and permanent form of body marking that has been utilised in various contexts, including law enforcement and forensic settings. It is evident that, due to their enduring and idiosyncratic character, they frequently surpass conventional biometric authentication methods, such as age or gender, in terms of their efficacy for individual identification. Nonetheless, conventional tattoo retrieval methodologies were contingent on the utilisation of keywords or other manually implemented techniques [Mc00]. The utilisation of methodologies such as the tattoo labelling in a dataset, e.g., 'dragon' or 'bird', was found to be both inconsistent and inadequate, owing to the considerable variability and intricacy inherent in tattoo designs [NG15]. To address these issues, researchers have begun to utilise content-based tattoo retrieval methods, which utilise visual information. Nonetheless, methodologies such as SIFT and SURF are effective in general image matching contexts [Li09]. However, their efficacy is diminished in scenarios involving tattoo images that are subject to distortion, partial visibility, or poor image quality. Consequently, these methodologies frequently prove ineffective in real-world scenarios [Go24]. Recent deep learning frameworks like SuperGlue enhance matching accuracy by enforcing geometric consistency via attention-based graph networks [Sa20]. Though designed for general

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matching, they can be adapted for tattoo retrieval. Nevertheless, in circumstances where image conditions are challenging, these methods frequently demonstrate deficiencies. This underscores the necessity for enhanced generalisation capabilities [LSP23].

OmniGlue, a recently developed and potentially significant model, employs advanced foundation models such as DINOv2 and cross-attention mechanisms to enhance robustness and generalisation [Ji24]. Building on this model, the present paper proposes a novel integrated framework that combines OmniGlue’s robust global feature extraction with LightGlue’s precise geometric refinement, with mathematical and logical enhancements. The BIVTatt database has been utilised for parameter optimisation of the framework. To validate the framework, the challenging WebTattoo dataset is employed in both closed-set and open-set scenarios.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Sect. 2 reviews existing literature on tattoo retrieval, with a focus on recent developments in deep learning and feature-matching approaches. Sect. 3 details the proposed framework. The experimental setup, including datasets, evaluation metrics, and protocol definitions, is described in Section 4. In Sect. 5, we present a comprehensive evaluation of our method, comparing it to a state-of-the-art baseline. Finally, Sect. 6 concludes the paper with a summary of key findings and suggestions for future research directions.

2 Related Work

In recent years, the landscape of tattoo image retrieval has advanced significantly, driven by deep learning and multi-task architectures. Early deep-learning solutions combined tattoo detection with identity retrieval in a unified framework. For instance, Han et al. [Ha19] proposed an end-to-end network that jointly performed tattoo detection and compact representation learning via shared convolutional neural network (CNN) features and auxiliary loss branches, achieving strong large-scale search performance on public benchmarks and a custom sketch dataset.

An applied 2024 system combined YOLOv5 for real-time tattoo detection with classical similarity measures (cosine and Euclidean) for identification [Po24]. Experimental evaluation on the deMSI dataset demonstrated that the proposed system achieved $mAP \approx 0.60$ and rank-1 identification rates up to 98%. A conservative similarity threshold of 0.15 (cosine) yielded full recall while reducing manual verification by about 20%. Other lines of work explored finetuning pretrained CNN backbones (ResNet, VGG, DenseNet architectures) and applying attention pooling to adapt intermediate feature maps for tattoo embedding tasks [NDMGMV19, NDMGMV22]. These methods achieved competitive retrieval performance, often without extensive domain-specific training datasets, even using off-the-shelf deep neural networks.

A significant advancement in tattoo retrieval was introduced by Gonzalez-Soler et al. [Go24] in the form of TattTRN (Template Reconstruction Network) [Go24]. This model employs a generative mapping that reconstructs a canonical tattoo template from an input image, enabling better inter-class separation and increased resilience to visual distortion. Notably,

Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed tattoo retrieval pipeline. OmniGlue and LightGlue independently extract keypoints, with matches filtered via KD-tree and scored using softmax-weighted integration.

the model was trained on a large-scale, semi-synthetic dataset, generated in virtual environments, which effectively addressed one of the core limitations in tattoo research: the scarcity of large, annotated datasets [Go24, GSRF23]. This synthetic training data spans thousands of tattoo instances across hundreds of categories and provides strong supervision for both reconstruction and embedding learning. TattTRN achieved state-of-the-art performance, i.e., identification rates of 81.6% and roughly 99% at rank-1 and rank-20, respectively, on challenging datasets such as WebTattoo and BIVTatt. By integrating synthetic data generation and generative reconstruction in a unified framework, the paper sets a new benchmark for tattoo retrieval systems.

Despite the advances made in this field, existing frameworks often prove inadequate when subjected to real-world conditions, such as poor image quality or other issues. It is hypothesised that a combination of OmniGlue’s global contextual robustness and LightGlue’s geometric matching has the potential to solve these limitations. While both models have been explored in the extant literature, their combination, the objective of this paper, has not been explored yet.

3 Methodology

The framework proposed in this paper integrates OmniGlue and LightGlue, augmenting their outputs through a series of logical and mathematical operations, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Both models independently extract keypoints from the query and enrolment images. OmniGlue utilises SuperPoint, a local keypoint detector that generates robust descriptors, in conjunction with DINOv2[Oq23], a self-supervised Vision Transformer that extracts high-level global semantic features. For each keypoint pair, OmniGlue assigns a confidence score representing the likelihood of a correct coincidence [Ji24]. LightGlue also leverages SuperPoint to extract local keypoints and their corresponding descriptors. These descriptors are processed through a dedicated transformer-based architecture designed to refine matches and enforce geometric consistency across layers. Additionally, LightGlue computes reliability scores for each keypoint, indicating the reliability and likelihood of a successful coincidence [LSP23].

The strength of OmniGlue lies in its robust generalisation capabilities, particularly under domain shift and appearance variation, while LightGlue excels in geometric precision and local spatial consistency. To combine the complementary strengths of both models, their output matches are cross-validated using a **KD-tree** approach: only those OmniGlue keypoint matches that lie in the proximity of LightGlue anchor points are retained. This cross-filtering mechanism integrates OmniGlue’s comprehensive semantic matching with LightGlue’s precise geometric filtering, resulting in a more reliable and noise-tolerant matching pipeline.

Despite their strengths, both models can fail in tandem, particularly in ambiguous or repetitive regions, resulting in dense clusters of incorrectly matched keypoints within small areas. Since a valid tattoo match should exhibit spatially broad keypoint coverage, such clustering is a strong indicator of a false positive. To suppress these invalid matches, a **Spatial Spread Penalty** δ is applied. This penalty is derived from the standard deviation of the (x_i, y_i) coordinates of the matched keypoints, normalised by the diagonal length of the image. A low δ indicates poor spatial coverage, while a higher δ reflects broad match distribution. To improve robustness, thresholds δ_{\min} and δ_{\max} are introduced:

- If $\delta \leq \delta_{\min}$, the maximum penalty is applied ($\delta = 0$),
- If $\delta \geq \delta_{\max}$, no penalty is applied ($\delta = 1$),
- Otherwise, the penalty is scaled linearly as:

$$f(\delta) = \frac{\delta - \delta_{\min}}{\delta_{\max} - \delta_{\min}}. \quad (1)$$

The final similarity score $\sigma(R, P)$ between the enrolled image R and query sample P is computed as $\sigma(R, P) = \omega \cdot \delta$, where ω represents the aggregate match strength and is calculated using a softmax-weighted integration:

$$\omega = \frac{1}{\beta} \log \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \exp(\beta \cdot c_i) \right), \quad (2)$$

where β is a scaling factor that emphasises stronger similarities.

If $\omega < 0.2$, indicating uncertain or weak comparison confidence, a **Fallback Rescoring Strategy** is triggered. This strategy aggregates the results of four alternative classification methods:

1. The above comparison model, but with doubled spatial tolerance to recover suppressed valid matches;
2. OmniGlue-only, bypassing LightGlue filtering;

3. LightGlue-only, bypassing OmniGlue scores;
4. A global semantic comparison using DINOv2 (Vit-L-14) [Oq23], an enhanced Vision Transformer that produces a high-level *CLS embedding* for each image.

The CLS embedding computed by DINOv2 (Vit-L-14) [Oq23] offers a global descriptor of each image’s content and layout. The similarity between two images is computed via cosine similarity between their CLS vectors:

$$\text{Similarity}(R, P) = \frac{\langle \text{CLS}_R, \text{CLS}_P \rangle}{\|\text{CLS}_R\| \cdot \|\text{CLS}_P\|}, \quad (3)$$

where a higher value reflects stronger global similarity.

Each fallback strategy ranks the top- k enrolled candidates independently (with $k = 20$), and a voting system is employed to combine the results. To emphasise semantic alignment, DINOv2 rankings are weighted three times higher than the others. A gap-aware heuristic is applied: if a candidate is significantly worse than the best (based on a predefined margin), it is penalised.

The resulting aggregate ranks are converted into preliminary confidence scores using a linear decay function. These scores are then multiplied by the candidate’s DINOv2 (Vit-L-14) cosine similarity, and a rank-based penalty is applied to discourage inconsistent comparisons. The candidate with the lowest overall score across all metrics is selected as the final candidate.

4 Experimental Setup

The experimental evaluation is designed to conduct an ablation study assessing the contributions of different components within the proposed framework, under both closed-set and open-set identification scenarios. A total of five configurations are evaluated, including the complete framework introduced in this paper. The second and third configurations isolate the performance of the framework when using only OmniGlue or only LightGlue, respectively, in order to demonstrate the benefit of their integration. The fourth configuration corresponds to the full framework with the **Fallback Rescoring Strategy** disabled, assessing its impact on difficult queries. The fifth configuration finally evaluates the standalone performance of DINOv2 (ViT-L/14) using CLS-based global similarity. Finally, all configurations are compared against the current state-of-the-art tattoo retrieval method, TattTRN [Go24], to contextualise performance improvements.

4.1 Databases

This work utilises two benchmark datasets: WebTattoo [Ha19] and BIVTatt [NDMGMV19]. As noted in prior work [Go24], tattoo identification tends to yield higher identification

Fig. 2: Example images from the two datasets used in this study. (a) WebTattoo samples, characterised by low resolution, occlusions, and varying acquisition conditions. (b) BIVTatt samples, which generally exhibit higher image quality and reduced visual distortion.

rates on the BIVTatt dataset. This is primarily due to its higher image quality and reduced levels of deformation, which make the retrieval task less challenging compared to WebTattoo. Consequently, the model parameters for the proposed framework were optimised on the easier BIVTatt dataset and subsequently evaluated on the more challenging WebTattoo dataset. This approach is based on the assumption that models performing well under more difficult, real-world conditions, such as those presented by WebTattoo, will naturally generalise to easier datasets. Fig. 2 shows examples of both databases.

In the following section, we detail the parameters, configurations, and implementation aspects of the proposed tattoo retrieval framework that integrates OmniGlue and LightGlue. All hyperparameters were empirically determined through iterative experimentation on BIVTatt and directly evaluated on the WebTattoo dataset without further tuning.

4.2 Implementation Details

The proposed framework was implemented using the PyTorch deep learning library and evaluated on an NVIDIA CUDA-enabled GPU. OmniGlue serves as the backbone component, using official pre-trained weights and combining SuperPoint (configured for 2,048 keypoints) with DINOv2 (ViT-B-14) [Oq23] for global semantic feature extraction. LightGlue operates on the same SuperPoint keypoints to perform local geometric matching and filtering. All models retain default hyperparameters. Match cross-validation between OmniGlue and LightGlue uses a KD-tree with radius scaling $r = 2.0$. To compute match confidence, the Softmax-weighted integration is applied with a scaling factor $\beta = 20$. A spatial

spread penalty is used to penalise clustered matches, using $\delta_{\min} = 0.03$ and $\delta_{\max} = 0.35$ as thresholds.

If the final score $\omega < 0.20$, a **Fallback Rescoring Strategy** is triggered. This includes a relaxed OmniGlue configuration ($r = 4.0$), removal of LightGlue filtering, and global semantic comparison using DINOv2 (ViT-L/14). CLS embeddings are ranked using a gap-aware mechanism, penalising candidates whose scores fall more than 0.1 below the top match and applying a rank offset boost of 8.

In the final voting stage, all methods are equally weighted, except for DINOv2, which is given triple weight due to its semantic robustness. Scores decay linearly from 0.20 to 0.01 across the top-20 ranks and are adjusted by DINOv2 similarity and a rank-based penalty using, i.e., $\text{score} = \text{decay} \cdot \text{similarity} \cdot (1.0 - 0.5 \cdot \text{norm_rank})$

4.3 Evaluation Metrics

To assess the proposed framework in both closed-set and open-set scenarios, we adopt standard biometric evaluation metrics from ISO/IEC 19795-1 [IS21], including the Cumulative Match Characteristic (CMC) curve, False Positive Identification Rate (FPIR), False Negative Identification Rate (FNIR), and Detection Error Trade-Off (DET) curve.

In closed-set identification, the CMC curve reflects the proportion of correctly identified samples whose true match appears within the top- k ranked enrolled results. It provides a cumulative distribution of the identification rate (IR) over increasing ranks.

In open-set settings, the system must also reject impostor probes. Two key metrics apply:

- **FPIR**: Proportion of non-mated comparisons incorrectly accepted by the system (i.e., score above threshold).
- **FNIR**: Proportion of mated comparisons incorrectly rejected by the system (i.e., score below threshold).

The DET curve plots FNIR against FPIR across thresholds, offering a comprehensive view of performance trade-offs under different operating conditions.

5 Results and Discussion

The goal of this section is twofold. Sect . 5.1 presents and discusses the closed-set identification performance of the models on the WebTattoo, while Sect. 5.2 reports the open-set identification performance of the same models and database.

Model	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10
TattTRN [Go24]	80.71	85.28	86.93	88.35	89.46	89.98	90.44	90.96	91.47	91.82
OmniGlue only	58.47	68.81	76.19	79.63	83.55	86.50	88.22	88.96	90.68	91.41
LightGlue only	77.37	80.58	82.05	83.52	84.99	85.73	85.73	86.72	87.70	88.92
OG+LG+Spread	79.34	83.02	84.99	85.74	87.46	88.45	89.20	89.69	89.69	89.93
DINOv2	88.69	94.59	96.07	96.80	96.80	96.80	97.29	97.29	97.78	98.03
Full Framework	90.91	95.59	96.57	96.57	96.82	97.06	97.30	97.80	97.80	98.29

Tab. 1: Top-10 rank-based mean identification rates (%) for six models, averaged across 10-fold cross-validation on WebTattoo. The best performance is highlighted in bold.

5.1 Closed-set Evaluation

A 10-fold cross-validation protocol was employed for the closed-set evaluation. As shown in Tab. 1, the proposed Full Framework achieves a top-performing, thus reporting a rank-1 IR of 90.91%, significantly outperforming all other configurations. In contrast, OmniGlue alone achieves only 58.47% at rank-1, highlighting the substantial performance gain achieved through integration and refinement within the proposed framework. The second-best performer, DINOv2 (Vit-L-14) [Oq23], reaches an IR of 88.69% at rank-1, remaining slightly behind the Full Framework despite its semantic strength. LightGlue, when used independently, performs better than OmniGlue at lower ranks, achieving an IR of 77.37% at rank-1, but is eventually overtaken by OmniGlue in higher ranks, demonstrating weaker overall rank scalability. The configuration referred to as OG+LG+Spread, which corresponds to the proposed framework without the fallback module, yields an IR of 79.34% at rank-1, indicating that the fallback strategy contributes a substantial boost to early-rank IRs. The TattTRN approach [Go24], representing the state-of-the-art in tattoo retrieval, achieves an IR of 80.71% at rank-1, which is approximately 10 percentage points lower than the proposed method and 91.82% at rank-10. Although the performance gap between methods narrows at higher ranks, the Full Framework consistently remains superior, achieving an IR of 98.29% at rank-10. Overall, the results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed approach, both in early retrieval ranks and across the top-10 identification range. The performance trend across 20 ranks is further illustrated in Fig. 3a.

5.2 Open-set Evaluation

The open-set evaluation measures the framework’s ability to distinguish between genuine matches and impostor queries, i.e., queries for which no corresponding biometric identifier exists in the enrolment. As in the closed-set protocol, a 10-fold cross-validation setup is adopted. In each fold, images are used as query samples and compared against enrolled images from both the same and a different fold. This design ensures that half of the comparisons are genuine and half are impostors, providing a balanced distribution for score analysis.

Tab 2 presents the FNIR at various operating points of FPIR, along with the Equal Error Rate (EER) for all models. At low FPIR levels (1.5%), the standalone LightGlue com-

Fig. 3: Performance comparison: (a) closed-set evaluation via CMC, (b) open-set performance via DET curve.

ponent achieves the lowest FNIR of 30.00%, indicating its strong discriminative power when minimising false positives is critical. However, as the operating threshold becomes more permissive, the proposed Full Framework (OmniGlue + LightGlue) outperforms all others. Specifically, at 15% and 20% of FPIR, it reports FNIRs of just 6.94% and 5.56%, respectively, which are substantially lower than both TattTRN and the individual component models. The superiority of the Full Framework is further confirmed by its EER, which stands at 11.56%, the lowest among all evaluated models. In comparison, TattTRN yields an EER of 20.75%, LightGlue reaches 20.77%, and OmniGlue performs worst at 30.54%. These findings demonstrate that while LightGlue alone is well-suited for applications requiring a very low FNIR at strict security thresholds, the integrated OmniGlue + LightGlue approach offers a more robust and balanced performance across a range of operating conditions. Notably, it provides a substantial improvement in distinguishing between genuine and impostor probes in open-set identification scenarios. The open-set performance, which shows the superiority of the proposed Full Framework for higher security thresholds, is further illustrated in Fig. 3b.

Model	EER	FNIR@FPIR					
		1.5%	5%	15%	20%	30%	40%
TattTRN [Go24]	20.75	65.64	36.92	25.20	21.23	15.07	11.28
OmniGlue + LightGlue	11.56	55.28	29.17	6.94	5.56	4.72	3.33
OmniGlue only	30.54	55.56	46.94	41.67	38.33	31.39	22.22
LightGlue only	20.77	30.00	27.50	23.33	21.11	17.50	16.11

Tab. 2: Benchmark of different framework components (in terms of FNIR and FPIR in %) at different operating points.

Fig. 4: Examples of correctly and wrongly classified samples.

6 Conclusions

This paper proposes a modular framework for tattoo image retrieval that integrates OmniGlue’s high-level semantic matching with LightGlue’s precise geometric alignment. By combining and refining outputs through mathematical strategies such as KD-tree filtering, softmax aggregation, and spatial spread penalties, the framework delivers notable gains in retrieval performance. On the WebTattoo dataset, it achieves a rank-1 identification rate of 90.91%, outperforming OmniGlue (58.47%), LightGlue (77.37%), and the prior state-of-the-art TattTRN (80.71%). It also performs strongly in open-set scenarios, with an EER of 11.56%, significantly lower than TattTRN (20.75%) and LightGlue (20.77%). However, this performance comes at a cost. While TattTRN and DINOv2 complete evaluations in seconds, the proposed framework requires up to 3 hours due to dense matching, filtering, and fallback stages. Although partly due to unoptimised code, structural complexity remains a bottleneck, motivating future efficiency improvements. Failure cases typically involve partial tattoos, occlusions, or distortions. As shown in Fig. 4, incorrect comparisons often have spatially concentrated keypoints with inflated confidence. These examples suggest future enhancements in spatial reasoning and confidence calibration are needed for robustness in real-world conditions.

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